

What makes you tick: an investigation of the pleasure needs of different population segments.

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What makes you tick: an investigation of the pleasure needs of different population segments.

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Abstract

The RealPeople project at Loughborough University is an Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC) funded research programme. The aim of the project is to address the growing need for tools that aid designers in understanding the emotional needs of different population segments. The project has resulted in the development of an interactive database that allows designers to browse statistically analysed data relevant to a general population, and more intimate subjective data about specific individuals, their lifestyles, and the products that they love. This allows them to gain a better understanding of the emotional and aspirational needs of different market groups, giving them a greater sense of empathy with people for when they are designing.

Keywords: pleasure, design resource, empathy, designer needs

Introduction

There is strong evidence to suggest that in today's market, consumers seek products that engage on an emotional level; ones that induce delight and pleasure, rather than those that are simply usable, or merely fulfil a role (Jordan, 1999, 2000). However, in recent years, with the growth of the inclusive design movement, and a shift in focus towards user centred design strategies, design and industry have begun to change from being predominantly technology driven to becoming increasingly driven by human needs.

The discipline of ergonomics has already facilitated the shift towards a human driven design process through informing designers on issues such as the physical and cognitive attributes of specific users. Now, an increasing number of ergonomists are applying their more rigorous scientific methods in the emerging field of design and emotion in an attempt to better understand the emotional and aspirational needs of the consumer; taking a more inclusive view of the individual, as well as the population as a whole.

Traditionally, designers satisfy the emotional and aspirational needs of the consumer through intuitive techniques, with no formal methodology. However, research has shown that providing designers with data that assists them in their awareness of the emotional needs of a target market is something that is much sought after (Chhibber et al. 2004). Furthermore, as the rest of the design process has become highly structured and reliable, design as an activity needs to follow suit; there is a need to understand what makes certain products successful to different market groups; and crucially, how this can be replicated for subsequent and different products (Green, 2002).

Tools to aid designers

Methods have been developed that allow designers to formally address the pleasurable aspects of products in the design process e.g. Kansei engineering (Nagamachi, 1995), or SEQUAM (Bandini-Buti et al. 1997). However these methods are statistically cumbersome, and implemented late in the design process, often after critical design decisions have already been made. More recently, methods have been developed that can be used at an earlier stage in the design process e.g. User Compass Chart (Sperling, 2005). Such methods however can be

quite time consuming and there is the risk that less technical designers may be reluctant to use them without appropriate support (Porter and Porter, 1999).

The RealPeople project differs in several ways. The majority of emotion related tools available to the designer are product focused, assessing variations in product design and the resulting human reaction. The RealPeople resource has been developed from a human-centred perspective, looking at general trends across a population in terms of attitudes towards design, and at specific people, their lifestyles, and the products that they find pleasurable. The resource was developed with designers' needs in mind (Chhibber et al. 2004), and is suitable for use at the beginning of the design process, to guide and focus the design direction.

The project builds upon a previous study (Porter et al. 2002) in which data concerning peoples' attitudes towards the pleasure giving properties of the products they own were collected and classified against the 'four-pleasure' framework developed by Jordan(1999); physio-pleasure, socio-pleasure, psycho-pleasure and ideo-pleasure. From this data, a basic paper based database of peoples' most pleasurable products was developed and informal evaluation by designers indicated that the development of a more extensive 'pleasure' resource would be of great value to them. The data also showed several indicative trends that did not reach statistical significance; but warranted future research across a wider sample.

Developing RealPeople

A series of interviews with both academic and practicing designers formed the starting point of the development of the RealPeople resource (Chhibber et al. 2004). These interviews not only verified the need for such a resource, but provided specific information that would guide the development of the resource in terms of its functionality, the manner in which it operated, and the data that would form its content.

There was clear evidence from the interviews that two different sets of data were required to satisfy the needs of designers; data that showed general trends across a wider population, and more intimate data about people, their lifestyles, and the products that they find pleasurable. These data were collected in two research strands that ran concurrently during the project.

General trend data

The first was the collection of general trend data concerning attitudes towards functionality, usability, product pleasure and product preference. A street survey was conducted in 11 UK locations (including London, Cardiff, Edinburgh and Nottingham), in all 582 people were interviewed. Participants completed an attitude questionnaire where they were asked to select from a number of statements the one which best described their feelings towards a particular aspect of product functionality, usability and each of the four pleasures e.g. 'the touch and feel of a product is important to me'. A quota sampling method was used to ensure an even spread across gender and age.

Intimate data

The second activity involved the collection of richer, more intimate data from 100 people. Each participant took part in an in-depth interview where they discussed their three most pleasurable products. Each interview took place in the participant's home or a personalised work space; showing their chosen products in, as far as practicably possible, their natural environment. It also allowed the interview session to be conducted in as a relaxed and informal manner as possible, to facilitate the collection of such intimate data.

Each interview is then edited into three, 2-3 minute film clip (one for each product) that encapsulates the most pertinent reasons as to why that product brings pleasure to the individual. These reasons are also summarised in short text bullet points with the 'four pleasures' used as a framework. A quota sampling method was again used to ensure an even spread across age and gender, and to give designers a more 'inclusive' design outlook, by providing as broad a range of people as possible. This data collection is nearly completed, with over 80 individuals interviewed.

As well as an in-depth interview where they discuss each of their three most pleasurable products, participants complete a questionnaire. The questionnaire was developed through several pilot studies and its content was strongly influenced by the views of practicing designers (Chhibber et al. 2004). The questionnaire is subdivided into several sections, and is filled in, in part by the interviewer, and in part by the participant; allowing the process to feel more informal and relaxed:

- Lifestyle – a series of open ended questions regarding different aspects of a person’s life e.g. leisure activities, favourite music and career aspirations. The aim of including this information is to immerse the designer in each individual’s lifestyle.
- Pleasure attitude questionnaire – this was the same as used in the general survey; this pool of data will be added to the general data set. It also gives the designer a brief overview of each person’s general opinions towards pleasure in products.
- Brand choice – participants list several brands that they like, aspire to, or feel reflect their personality. These data are included to satisfy the need, specified by designers, to understand the aspirations of different individuals.
- Style choice – participants are presented with images showing a sample of products from four product categories: mobile phones, chairs, fonts, and wristwatches. Each category has five examples selected through a focus group with designers, to represent the style possibilities in that category i.e. 5 mobile phones that were chosen as they reflected the full breadth of the mobile phone market at that time. The participants select which one of the 5 samples in each category they like the most, and briefly explain why. This will enhance the designer’s understanding of particular users and their aesthetic preferences.
- Personality assessment – each participant completes a short personality assessment. The test is based on the Big Five personality locator (Gleitman et al. 2000).

Trend data

The data provided by the 582 respondents to the trend data survey were entered into the statistics package SPSS and analysed to identify any trends. A non-parametric χ^2 test was employed in two ways; as a test of fit, and as a test of independence, to identify trends across the entire sample population and trends across gender and age. The attitude questionnaire data from the smaller sample of 100 participants in the ‘intimate’ survey will be included when the data collection is complete. A number of trends were identified at $p < 0.05$ but only those that reached a significance of $p < 0.01$ are presented due to space limitations.

Population wide trends

The χ^2 was used as a test of fit; showing a number of significant trends across the entire sample population.

Functionality

The sample population showed a preference towards products that have the exact functionality required (41%), or slightly higher levels of functionality that can be explored (42%). There was a low appreciation of products with more functionality than will be used (9%), or maximum functionality (8%).

Usability

There was a clear preference across the sample population for products that are simple and easy to use (60%), with 27% of the sample preferring products that are initially a challenge to use but easy to use once familiar.

Physio-pleasure

The shape and form of a product was important to 66% of the sample population and was the most valued of all of the physio-pleasure characteristics for the sample. Colour and tactility of the product are very important to 60% of the sample. Conversely, only 39% of the sample felt that the sound that a product makes in use was important to them.

Socio-pleasure

Only 33% were interested in products that demonstrate that they have discerning taste to others and 19% were interested in products that demonstrate that they are successful. Few were interested in products that tell other people something about them e.g. sports watch. 38% like products that are a talking point amongst their friends and/or family, with less people being interested in products that are a talking point amongst any group of people. 62% of the sample valued products that could suit any social context and 40% liked products that facilitated social interaction e.g. a mobile phone.

Psycho-pleasure

The results for this product characteristic correspond closely with the results for usability; however this psycho-pleasure attribute relates more to the sense of satisfaction from task completion and the ability to achieve this easily. 82% liked products that allowed them to complete tasks easily. The majority of the sample (71%) found products with personal significance to them to be appealing.

Ideo-pleasure

63% of the sample population like products that represented an ideology that they believed in e.g. eco-friendly. A large number of the sample (72%) valued the overall aesthetics of a product. However the sample did not show any particular preference for designer/branded products.

Age trends

A χ^2 analysis was used as a test of independence in order to identify whether the results, when viewed across participant age, varied to a great enough extent to indicate an effect. A number of significant age effects were found.

Functionality

The older age groups prefer products that display exact functionality. This is mirrored by a trend of younger age groups preferring products with more functionality that they can explore, whilst increasingly older age groups finding this less appealing.

Usability

A high percentage (60%) of the subjects preferred products that are simple and easy to use; the data indicates that a high proportion of these are from the older age groups, e.g. 83% of the 56+ age group, compared with a lower proportion of the younger age groups e.g. 43% of 18-25 year old age group and 50% of the 26-35 year old age group. A low proportion (27%) of the sample preferred products that were initially challenging to use, but after some ownership were easy to use. However, a higher proportion of that 27% are from the younger age groups (31% of 18-25, and 36% of 26-35); indicating that younger age groups are more willing to use products that require a level of learning or are a challenge to use. The percentage of the 56+ age range seeking a similar level of usability was markedly less at 17%. This highlights the fact that younger age ranges tend to be more comfortable with technology and with learning to use it.

Physio-pleasure

The younger age groups appear to value the colour of products to a greater extent than older age groups (72% of 18-25 year olds compared to just 47% of the 56+ category). A similar age effect is seen with the tactile aspects of products e.g. 71% of 26-35 year olds compared to

49% of 56+ year olds. There was not a significant effect when considering the sound that a product makes and the overall form of products.

Socio-pleasure

The 26-35 age group (46%) are significantly more interested in products that demonstrate discerning taste to others in contrast to the other age groups in the sample e.g. 36-45, 27.8%, and 56+, 26%. The younger age group are also more interested in products that tell other people something about themselves (18-25, 40%, compared to 46-55, 12%). Across the sample, there is a general trend of a reduced appreciation of products that tell people something about them with increasing age. The younger age groups are also more interested in products that are a talking point amongst family and friends (18-25, 50%, 46-55, 20%) and in products that are a talking point amongst any group of people; evaluation of this product characteristic across the entire sample population showed that it did not appear to be of great importance (20% valued it). However, of this low proportion, the younger age groups found this aspect more appealing than the older groups. They are also more interested in products that allow them to socialise (e.g. 18-25, 49%, 56+, 27%). The middle age groups also showed a greater preference for products that are understated (e.g. 63% of 36-45 year olds, compared to 46% of 18-25 year old, or 43% of 56+ year olds).

Psycho-pleasure

The only significant trend for this pleasure was that younger age groups tended to find greater pleasure from products that express their personality than older age groups e.g. 73% of 18-25 year olds, compared to just 27% of the 56 and over age range.

Ideo-pleasure

It is evident from looking at the data that the overall aesthetics of product is an important characteristic to the sample population. However, when viewed across age, there is a steadily reducing appreciation of this characteristic as the age groups get older e.g. 18-25 year olds 82.7%, compared to 60% of the 56+ age group. Similarly, younger age groups seem to gain more pleasure from products by a particular designer than older age groups, for example, 26.5% of 26-35 year olds compared to 10% of 56+ year olds stated that they found such products pleasurable. There are no apparent age effects in the appeal of products that represent an ideology or loyalty to a particular brand.

Gender trends

The χ^2 test was again used as a test of independence and it showed that there were a number of significant gender differences.

Functionality

45% of females and 36% of males have a preference for products that have the exact functionality required; the difference approaches significance. This trend is counterbalanced by a slight preference in males (45% compared to 39% of females) towards products that have additional functionality that can be explored.

Usability

The responses demonstrate that males and females have similar attitudes towards product usability; a desire for products that are either simple and easy to use, or perhaps challenging when initially used.

Physio-pleasure

There was a clear gender effect when considering product colour, with 70.2% of the female sample valuing colour as a product characteristic compared with just 48.9% of the male population. Although product sound was valued by only 39% of the total sample, the data when viewed across gender shows an effect. 45% of the males in the sample population valued this characteristic compared to just 33.8% of the females. There were no other apparent gender effects.

Socio-pleasure

When analysed across gender, it was evident that males (38.2%) showed a preference for products that demonstrate a discerning taste more than females (26.5%). Females, however, find more pleasure in products that allow them to socialise; 47% compared with 34% of males.

Psycho-pleasure

The data showed that 52% of females gain significantly more pleasure from products that express an aspect of their personality, than males (45%). Females also experience more

pleasure from gifts that have a personal significance (77%) than males (64%). No other gender differences were identified.

Ideo-pleasure

The only major gender effect for ideo-pleasure was that 68.9% of females liked products that represent an ideology they believe in, compared to 57.1% of males.

The RealPeople DVD resource

The conclusions of the designer interviews (Chhibber et al. 2004) were developed into a design specification that guided the preliminary development of the resource, as well as the type of data that formed its contents. The resultant RealPeople database is a 'stand alone' DVD based resource (both Mac and PC compatible) with an interactive graphic 'front end' developed in Macromedia Director MX and the collected data being stored in a database accessed via the scripting language 'lingo'. The 'look' and 'feel' of the resource have been developed through an iterative design process using team members, other colleagues and designers for evaluation.

The principal page of interaction is the 'search page' (see Figure 1). The designer is able to search the database in a flexible and intuitive way. Selecting different icons allows the designer to filter the individuals in the database by criterion such as age, gender, or income; conversely, they can filter the data by specifying different product types. For example, selecting 'mobile phones' filters out everyone except those who chose their mobile phone as one of their most pleasurable products. As the designer defines the search parameters, the array of 100 individuals (grid at bottom of Figure 1) updates in 'real time' and fades out those individuals that have been eliminated. This highly visual feedback during the search process gives the designer a greater sense of which individuals they may be 'designing out' during each search. The images of those that remain form the link that directs the designer to that individual's data set.

Figure 1: search page showing selection categories and photographs of 100 individuals in the database.

Figures 2-6 illustrate the different subsets of information available for each of the participants. Each person has in essence, their own individual homepage that remains consistent on the left hand side of the screen (aiding navigation). Access to each different data set for that individual is done through interacting with this homepage, the right window updating to show that data set in full.

As a default, each individual's page appears with the 3 product video clips on display in the right window (as these are part of the search criterion). Each video clip is highly immersive, thought provoking, and is selected to encourage empathy between the designer and each individual in the database. In addition to this, a table of bullet points of the most pertinent reasons why the product brings them pleasure, analysed and presented with respect to the four pleasure framework, is provided as a quick reference for the designer.

Figure 2: individual 'home' page and product videos

Figure 3: individual 'home' page and more product information

Figure 4: individual 'home' page and lifestyle information

Figure 5: 'home' page and style choice data

Figure 6: 'home' page and brand choice data

Added functionality

The RealPeople resource was developed with designers in mind. It has several functional features that are intended to enable them to use the resource more effectively, allowing it to fit in with the manner in which designers work. These are outlined below:

- Notes – each database individual has a text window in which designers can add and save notes about that person, either for personal use, or to be viewed by subsequent users.
- Slideshow – the designer can create basic slideshows containing information from the database. These can be saved and then shown as a presentation.
- View all videos – the designer can enter search criterion, then activate a 'play all video' function. This automatically plays all of the video clips relevant to that search consecutively; allowing the designer to take a more passive role and absorb the information at leisure.

- Portfolio – the designer can save relevant search results in individual project portfolios; these will be editable and also be able to be shown as slideshows. It is envisaged that multiple portfolios will be developed by the user as several projects may be running consecutively, each with its own relevant search criterion.
- History – allows the designer to view previous searches, similar to contemporary web browsers.
- Export – the ability to export notes and portfolios for use on other machines that have the RealPeople database installed, potentially allowing sharing of information across global design teams.

Feedback and future work

A beta version of the RealPeople resource was tested by designers from a number of UK design consultancies. Testing involved a brief demonstration of the resource and its functionality. Each designer then carried out several tasks (e.g. searching, creating a portfolio) that allowed them to fully experience the method of interaction and the functionality that was on offer. They were then asked to comment on different aspects of the resource, ranging from the quality of the data and its format, to the overall visual appeal. Feedback was extremely positive about all major aspects, with no major functional changes required.

Anecdotal evidence and that reported in the literature suggest that the large number of young practising designers find it difficult to empathise with their users using traditional techniques (Sanders, 1999). Therefore, inclusion of a disproportionate number of older participants is being considered to facilitate inclusive design. The underlying principles of visual information (in the form of video clips and high quality images) as a design research output, to inspire and immerse designers in peoples' lifestyles, is also being applied to other research projects being carried out by the researchers with a specific focus on the automotive interior.

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